

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th April 2021

Accepted: 27th April 2021

Online: 29th April 2021

KEY WORDS

Competence, knowledge, skills and abilities, teaching, activity, language, specialists.

TO THE QUESTION OF COMPETENCE APPROACH IN TEACHING BUSINESS ENGLISH

¹ Egamberdiyeva Dildora Usubjonovna

¹ Teacher of department of languages, faculty of agrolgy and business
Andijan Branch of Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727507>

ABSTRACT

Competence is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities formed in the process of teaching a particular discipline, as well as the ability to perform any activity based on the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

In the methodology and pedagogy, a different classification of competencies is distinguished, which are applied specifically and exclusively to foreign languages. Foreign language competence characterizes a certain level of language proficiency and includes three interrelated competences: linguistic, speech and communicative [6]. Communicative competence is the ability to solve by means of a foreign language the tasks of communication that are relevant for students in everyday life, educational, industrial and cultural life; the student's ability to use the facts of language and speech to realize the goals of communication.

Communication competence is at the core of Business English teaching. Business English learners not only need to know the language well, but also be able to use it in specific situations. Typically, communicative competence consists of the following components: linguistic competence, discourse competence and intercultural competence.

Linguistic competence includes the study of the basic components of the language such as grammar, vocabulary, phonetics.

Discourse competence presupposes the practical use of language, i.e. communication of people within a certain context. Business discourse includes oral and written communication within the framework of business communication. This includes negotiations, presentations, meetings, business correspondence, business communication in person, by phone, via the Internet.

Role-playing games, which are learning through action, play an important role in the development of communicative competence. This is one of the active learning methods widely used in the classroom. In this exercise, speech activity is considered in a social context, taking into account the topic of the conversation, the relationship between communication partners, the place and time of the action, taking into account the preliminary knowledge about the interlocutor, which contributes to the approach of the learning

process to real life. In a role-playing game, students play a specific role. Usually their behavior and remarks are determined by the data presented on the card. The language used in role-playing games is usually pre-learned and reinforced through this activity. Another feature of role-playing games is that each of the participants does not have all the relevant information. This allows you to develop foresight skills, language guess, etc.

Role-playing games contribute to the formation of the following skills:

- to accept and fulfill the role;
- choose language means according to the situation;
- to pursue and defend their point of view ;
- tend to compromise;
- provide for a conflict and find ways to eliminate it;
- to formulate a problem and propose ways to solve it;
- change the strategy of their behavior;
- to master the communication strategy (it is appropriate to use speech and etiquette formulas, know the formulas of appeals, be able to express gratitude, request, consent, objection) [3].

Presentations are one of the most effective ways to develop discourse competence. Presentations are communication situations where one person speaks and the others listen. Speaking about presentations, we proceed from the fact that this is not a presentation of a new product or idea, but in a broader sense - a monologue speech with elements of public speech. Here it is advisable to talk about the art of oratory. At the same time, a modern presentation is almost always accompanied by visual materials (slides, multimedia materials), which are characterized by a special functional language, similar to titles, annotations, essay plans. At the same time, new types of

presentations have appeared, which are associated with traditional speech accompanied by slides, only with individual elements.

Presentations can take place in different situations. An informal meeting of a small group over coffee can include a small presentation. A presentation for one person in an elevator is also possible. Presentations can also be directed to an audience of 200 people. Speaking skills are necessary here, but contrary to popular belief that the main thing is the content, the main thing in the presentation is what effect it has on the listener (how it is presented, how it is framed, etc.). A very important role is played here by the use of technical means - slides, computer technology. The main content of the presentation is presented in visual media. Teaching successful presentation skills includes many other skills in addition to language training. There are cases when, from a linguistic point of view, a presentation was flawless, but so boring and monotonous that the audience instantly lost interest in it. Conversely, a speaker who knows how to interest the audience and attract its attention is forgiven for shortcomings in terms of linguistic competence.

The course of Business English, therefore, allows you to integrate a variety of educational activities, which allows you to form and improve different competencies, both foreign language and other general and professional competencies highlighted at the university, among them:

a) system competences

- be able to carry out self-study;
- effectively present your project in English;
- be able to make independent decisions;

b) analytical competencies

- master the techniques of analysis and synthesis, including situational and complex analysis, comparative analysis;
 - to form and improve skills within the framework of IT competencies;
 - be able to work with multimedia materials;
- c) communication competencies**
- effectively carry out oral and written communication in all forms (oral and written) and types (types of communication are determined by the conditions of communication, the number of participants, the goals of communication and the nature of the situation) in English;
 - to conduct discussions on professional and business topics in English;
 - to speak publicly in situations of professional and business communication in English;
 - to work effectively in a team.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Nosirova M.K. Formation of foreign language communicative competence of students in the framework of modular program. International scientific journal. Economy and society. № 6(73) -s.: 2020.
2. Egamberdiyeva D.U. The account of individual features of students in the process teaching english language. International scientific journal. Economy and society. № 6(73) -s.: 2020.
3. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. Theory of teaching foreign languages. Linguodidactics and methodology: a textbook for students of linguistic universities and faculties of foreign languages of higher pedagogical educational institutions / N.D. Galskova, N.I. Gez. - 3rd edition, erased. - M. Publishing Center "Academy", 2006.
4. F.A. Tillabaeva. S.T. Jabbarova. The system of work on the use of terminological dictionaries in the educational process in universities. Scientific electronic journal. 2019., pp. 131-132.
5. Kiryigitov B., Nosirova M. Introduction & Purpose of the project: software facilities in translation. International conference. 2016, p. 268.
6. Shchukin, A.N. Linguodidactic encyclopedic dictionary: more than 2000 units / A.N. Shchukin. - M.: Astrel: AST: Keeper, 2007.
7. // Linguistics and Philosophie 2., 1978. S. 373-413.